

India's Vaccine Diplomacy and Regionalism

Dr. Rajiv M. Gupte

Prof. Anand N. Limaye

Abstract

India has been “Pharmacy of the World”. This has further been reinforced during COVID-19. Indian Vaccine has been found to be effective in containing the pandemic in many corners of the world. India delivered around 163mn doses of vaccine to 96 countries. India's *Maitri* Initiative and vaccine diplomacy was enacted as a result of which, Bangladesh, Myanmar, Nepal, Bhutan, Maldives, Sri Lanka and Afghanistan received vaccine from India. This was in tune with the Neighborhood first policy, this diplomacy and its impact has been studied in this paper. Using favorable opinion on pre and post COVID-19 is analyzed. India is further poised to supply “Malaria Vaccine” to 55 African countries, but its newer version would soon be supplied to South Asian neighbors. Marshall and Yee (2021) have argued that, India is trying to counter China by using its vaccine diplomacy to expand foreign relations avoid territorial conflict. Despite Nepali geographic and geo-political proximity to China, India took advantage of the opportunity to send vaccines to Nepal. Besides, looking at India neighborhood, a regional, robust approach in terms of trade is examined. This paper argues that, looking at the disruption of supply chain, regionalism to be strengthened. While a regional framework covering a particular issue brings specific cost-benefit structure to each member, generalization is possible to a certain degree. This paper looks at Game-theory model to study the inclusion of trade-partners like Japan and US. As India is leading the Global South, new initiatives like “Global Pandemic Treaty” and “Indo-Pacific Charter” is argued as, on the background of COVID-19.

Keywords – Vaccine Diplomacy, Soft power, Regionalism

Introduction

Even as India has established herself as “Pharmacy of the world”, the claim has been proven once again. India helped the neighboring nations and across the globe with COVID 19 vaccines during the pandemic. This is in tune with India's neighborhood first policy and

has indeed helped augment India's soft power. COVID 19 Pandemic had drastic impact on regional and global geopolitical architecture and India's image in neighborhood and extended neighborhood. In early 2021 India established "Neighborhood First" policy and propagated her role as net security provider in the region.

India had already established as a major player in export of pharmaceutical products to the extent of 23 billion dollars of export with target of 50 billion this year.

Figure 1. Region-wise distribution of India's pharmaceutical product exports.
 Source: Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India.

During pandemic many countries have been perusing global health diplomacy (Lisk and sehovic,2020). India decided not only to vaccinate her people but also to assist neighboring countries (Pattanaik 2021). As such India's relationship with her neighbors had not been very cordial, given the internal and external dynamics, however one remained a peace-loving country. The *Vasudhaiva Kutumbakam* has a pivotal place in India's foreign policy (Mahapatra 2016). India had supported her neighborhood at times of calamities, tsunamis, floods, earthquakes and also helped in space technology. While the neighboring countries were finding it difficult to contain COVID 19: India's neighborhood first policy has certainly helped them. The political, Socio economic and strategic landscape in India's neighborhood has been changing considerably.

India's diplomacy primarily centered on managing relations with the neighbors as can be traced back to Nehru's Panchsheel doctrine, to Gujaral doctrine based on principal on non-

reciprocity (Muni,2017). Since 1914 India's foreign policy witnessed the shift from idealism to realism.

1990 decade was watershed moment in south Asian regional cooperation as the world witnessed economic reforms. India is conscious in promoting regional cooperation thru trade and technological cooperation during this changing geopolitical architecture (Behuria,2012). The Gujaral doctrine played a key role in India's neighborhood policy enabling other countries to rise above the region security conundrum. India provided the neighboring countries with unilateral concession with seeking reciprocity. Subsequent governments provided national democratic alliance (1989-2004) and united progressive alliance (2004-2014). As a result, the trade and security relation with SAARC countries witnessed a dramatic shift.

But the real implementation of neighborhood first policy came in 2014. There have been many visits from the heads of SAARC and BIMSTEC countries. During the address in 69th UNGA the Indian prime minister stated that a nations destiny is linked to the neighborhood and that is why India's highest priority was advancing friendship and cooperation with the neighbors.

COVID 19 Pandemic emerged as a global health crisis. As a result, there was a serious threat to trade, global supply chain, health and other related aspects. There had to be collaborative efforts of regional organizations such as SAARC. Many south Asian countries reported a serious threat to health and economy. Despite the differences, Indian Prime minister proposed a joint emergency Fund based on health cooperation with an initial contribution of 10 million dollar, and with a pool of contribution it reached 21 million dollars (jha & jha,2020). Except for Pakistan all countries pledged to contribute directly to the SAARC COVID 19 emergency fund. Pakistan pledged 3 million dollars which would be deposited to SAARC secretariat. This action demonstrated the regional differences. As India is the biggest pharmacy in the world, the leadership realized the lead to play a significant role in health cooperation and vaccination. This was India's *Maitri* initiative.

COVID-19 vaccine supplies so far to its geographical neighbours as of May 2021.
 COVID-19 vaccine supplies so far to its neighbours (In lakhs)

Country	Grant			Commercial			COVAX			Total supplies
	Quantity	Date of despatch		Quantity	Date of despatch		Quantity	Date of despatch		
Maldives	0.5	0.5	7 February	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Bhutan	3.3	2.0	21 January	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		1.2	26 March	7.0	5.0	25 January	0.468	0.468	6 March	0.968
		0.1	2 April	-	2.0	22 February	-	-	-	10.3
	0.55	0.15	20 January	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		0.40	21 March	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0.2	0.1	20 January	0.1	0.1	29 March	0.012	0.012	6 March	0.55
	1.7	1.5	19 February	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		0.2	22 January	2.0	2.0	11 February	-	-	-	0.312
	1.1	1.0	11 February	-	-	-	-	-	-	3.7
		0.1	21 January	1.0	1.0	20 February	0.348	0.348	5 March	2.448
	-	-	28 March	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
	0.5	0.5	28 January	0.5	0.5	24 February	0.264	0.264	6 March	-
India's Geographical Neighbours										1.264
Other countries across the world, including India's Geographical Neighbours										19.542
India's Geographical Neighbours in India's total vaccine supply										66.370
										29.44%

External Affairs, Government of India, 2021.

Figure 2

India's Soft Power

This initiative positively affected India's Soft power not only in immediate neighborhood but also globally.

Bangladesh :

In April 26, 2021 Bangladesh sealed the orders with India to contain the spread of COVID 19. In October 2020 Bangladesh had declined china's offer of corona vaccine due to the efficacy. And as the purchase would have involved a clause on sharing cost of clinical trials. Bangladesh turned to India, as India contributes to 60% of global Vaccine production. In the past Few years public opinion about India in Bangladesh had suffered. In January 2020 India adopted CAA (citizen

amendment act) which triggered Protest in Bangladesh. Failure to sign the Ganges river water agreement was another issue. Bangladesh was the first country to receive vaccine from India under the *Maitri* initiative. In January 2021 Dacca received 3.3 million COVID-19 ELID vaccine's with further was raised to 10.3 million.

Beijing had been already making inroads with BRI (Belt and road initiative). China Also sought military alliance with Bangladesh. Although it never happened Bangladesh tried to maintain cordial relations with both India and china.

Country	Grant	Commercial	Total
India	3.3	7	10.3
China	0.5	0	0.5

Figure 3
Source: MEA Website

Nepal and Bhutan:

The mountain states faced heavy challenges during the pandemic. The vaccine *Maitri* initiative had a very positive effect on the relationship. India emerged a first responder to Bhutan and Nepal. Bhutan also reciprocated with a supply of 40 MTs of liquid oxygen. Nepal received 8 Lacs Doses from SINOPHARM, China in the past years had not so conducive relation with India, received about 100 million doses from India.

Country	India			China Grant
	Grant	Commercial	COVAX	
Nepal	1.1	1	0.34	0.8
Bhutan	0.55			

Figure 4
Source: MEA Website

Myanmar and Thailand:

Myanmar is strategically important for India as a gate way to India's North east region. Myanmar received 1.7 million doses from India, the military coup disrupted the trajectory of the Myanmar pandemic response. In Feb 2021 the health care workers and civil servants

across the country launched a national civil disobedience movement. There was also public resentment against China, it has been the key to the shielding of Myanmar in UNSC.

Vaccines provided by India (In million doses)			
Country	Grant	Commercial	Total
Myanmar	1.7	2	3.7
Vaccine provided by china (In million doses)			
Myanmar	0.5	0	0.5
Thailand	0.5	5.5	6

Figure 5
Source: MEA Website

India's other south east Asian neighbor, Thailand is also under pressure. There was public disapproval to the government decision to not join COVAX, which is subscribed to by almost the entire neighborhood. Thailand was among one of the countries that sent relief to India during the second wave as a part of Thailand's look west policy and is regarded as a rising market.

Here India needs to play a larger role.

Srilanka and Maldives:

These two nations were primarily looking at Russia and china's for vaccines. As a part of china's debt diplomacy were they mainly under the influence of India's northern neighbor. The bail out packages from India started positive disposition towards India. These countries began their vaccination drives primarily by utilizing donations from India. This led to a great deal of pro India rhetoric, with presidents of both countries taking to twitter to thank India for her generosity. Hey also declared in Feb 2021 that Srilanka was likely to have only India's COVISHEILD. Both countries following India's donation placed direct orders with Serum Institute India. However, due to lag in supplied they sought to source vaccines from china and Russia.

Country	India	China	Russia
Sri lanka	1,000,000	1,100,000	65,000
Maldives	30,00,000	2,00,000	-----

Figure 6
Source: MEA Website

Srilanka also received 65000 doses from Russia. Both Srilanka and Maldives had been concerned with India's difficulties during second wave and often explained the situation to their own public.

Pakistan and Afghanistan:

As India commenced the vaccine diplomacy, In January 2021, till March, India Did not receive any request for vaccine from Pakistan. Pakistan suffered a setback as it was highly dependent on COVAX. Pakistan had to reengineer its entire vaccine strategy, As India halted the exports of vaccine. Islamabad received 1.6 million doses from china. Pakistan offered to send relief material to India during initial onslaught of second wave. The conditional offer was to release all the Kashmiri prisoners on humanitarian grounds.

Country	India	China	Russia
Afghanistan	500,000	0	0
Pakistan	0	10,60,000	50,000

Figure 7

Source: MEA Website

Russia also supplied 50,000 doses of SPUTNIK V vaccines. While, Russia Pakistan ties are not very strong, Russia could possibly look at the stakes in Afghanistan thru Pakistan.

India has a lot of interest in Afghanistan, pertaining to central Asian energy markets and broader connectivity projects. Kabul received 1 Million doses in 2 phases. However, during 2nd wave they looked at china and Russia as alternative suppliers. In March 2021 US Secretary of state official included India in the process thru a plan for the future of Afghanistan that outlined the crucial role of regional actors including India.

The Result

Pew research data states that these Vaccine diplomacy efforts have sustainably improved the global views of India for enhancing India's soft power.

Global View of India

Country	Unfavorable	Favorable	After Pandemic
South. Korea	18	64	+5
Philippines	21	58	+2
Japan	24	8	+2
Indonesia	23	57	+15

Australia	33	57	+10
U. S	23	50	+15

Figure 8
Source- PEW data

Consequences

Vaccine diplomacy of India has immensely contributed to India's soft power. Such huge market, trained man power, advancements in Information technology, robust Institutional frame work and thriving democracy can be leveraged for regionalism. India's Neighborhood is not Devoid from regional framework's in various forms. SAARC, BIMSTEC & ASEAN are some of the established frame works. At this stage we suggest that this diplomacy needs to be extended to

- A. Regional Trade
- B. Global Pandemic treaty
- C. Asia Pacific charter

A. Regional Trade

The improved soft power of India needs to be translated into advancing the trade benefits. The paper presents a Hypothetical Framework using game theory. The rise and fall of various institution are a result of states regional choices in terms of their membership preferences. We look at proposing inclusion of Japan in this frame work and leave china at bay.

The role of the larger state Depends upon the gains which are relatively large while the costs are also large. Long lasting question on whether sponsoring frame work of institution is benefit or costly to the leader rests on benevolence or predatory hegemon, which side is emphasized.

	Number 1 state (leader)	Number 2 State
Benefit	Large (This becomes larger than the no.1 State considering Prestige to be critical)	Small
Cost	Large (This can be reduced by requesting the number 2	Small (this can be increased if the number 2 state is

	state to share the burden)	required to share the burden)
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Figure 8

Source: Shintaro Hamanaka (Asian development bank - Regionalism Cycle in Asia (-Pacific) page no.2)

JAPAN

	No framework	Asia- only framework	Japans active participation	Japans active participation
Benefit	None	Extremely Large	Small	Small
Cost	None	Large	Large	Medium
Net benefit	None (0)	Positive (2)	Negative (-2)	(-1)

Figure 8.

Source: Shintaro Hamanaka (Asian development bank - Regionalism Cycle in Asia (-Pacific) page no.3)

CHINA

	No framework	Asia- only framework	Japans active participation	Japans active participation
Benefit	None	Negative	Medium	Medium
Cost	None	None	Very small	Large
Net benefit	None (0)	Negative (-2)	Positive (2)	(-1)

Figure 9.

Source: Shintaro Hamanaka (Asian development bank - Regionalism Cycle in Asia (-Pacific) page no.3)

China	Participation	Non-participation
Japan		
Participation	-4,4	2,-2
Non-participation	-2,2	0,0

Figure 10

Source: MEA Website

Thus, it can be seen that inclusion of extra regional partner like Japan would add value to both the parties. We further suggest that India continues non-participation in RCEP (regional comprehensive economic partnership).

B. Global Pandemic Treaty

It has been proposed by WHO (world health organization) that regional pandemic treaty should be negotiated by the member states. We suggest that this treaty should be adopted Under article 21 instead of Article 19. Also, there may be public hearings and different stake holders including government, Industry representation, health care experts & legal opinion makers. This instrument needs to be binding under international law and

1. Ensure higher, sustained & long-term government engagement.
2. Early detection and prevention of pandemic.
3. Resilience and response Mechanism.
4. One health approach.

There should also be a compulsory licensing provision.

C. Indo Pacific charter

As the hegemonic designs of some regional players punctuate the peace and security of other nations, it would be appropriate for India to take lead in developing Indo pacific charter. At the juncture when India is preceding over 3 important institutions- G20, SCO, UNSC, it would only be appropriate if India spearheads this.

- A. Resilience of global supply chain.
- B. Respect for peace and sovereignty of their nations.
- C. Respect for Multilateral framework.
- D. Protecting Sea Lines of Communication.
- E. Transparency in Data Sharing.
- F. Regional Arms race.

Conclusion

During pandemic India has been a great contributor in vaccination programs in the region. The vaccine diplomacy juxta positioned with debt diplomacy has resulted into enhancement of India's Soft Power. While India has been a responsible power in the Indo pacific region and enjoying strong soft power status, should take lead in developing regional trade frame work, Global pandemic treaty and Indo pacific charter.

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